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THE HISTORY OF THE TRANSLATION OF THE UZBEK HISTORICAL NOVEL “O‘TKAN KUNLAR”

O‘ZBEK TARIXIY ROMANI “O‘TKAN KUNLAR”NING TARJIMASI TARIXI

ИСТОРИЯ ПЕРЕВОДА УЗБЕКСКОГО ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО РОМАНА “УТКАН КУНЛАР” (“МИНУВШИЕ ДНИ”)

O.A.Khamdamov- teacher, Namangan RCATPE

Annotation. This article deals with the translation of the famous Uzbek writer Abdulla Kadiri's novel “O‘tkan kunlar” into German and English. The article quotes well-known scholars' views on Abdulla Kadiri and his novel “O‘tkan kunlar”.

Key words. National traditions, history of Uzbek literature, comparative analysis, historical material, oriental method.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada atoqli o‘zbek adibi Abdulla Qodiriyning “O‘tkan kunlar” romanining nemis va ingliz tillariga tarjima qilish bilan bog‘liq masalalar yoritilgan. Maqolada Taniqli olimlarning Abdulla Qodiriy va uning “O‘tkan kunlar” romani haqidagi fikrlaridan na‘munalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Milliy an‘analar, o‘zbek adabiyoti tarixi, qiyosiy tahlil, tarixiy material, sharqona usul.

Аннотация. в статье рассматриваются вопросы перевода романа известного узбекского писателя Абдуллы Кадири “Уткан кунлар” на немецкий и английский языки, также цитируются взгляды известных ученых на творчество Абдуллы Кадири и его роман “Уткан кунлар”.

Ключевые слова: национальные традиции, история узбекской литературы, сравнительный анализ, исторический материал, восточная методика.

The economic and cultural ties of the Federal Republic of Germany with Uzbekistan are strengthening year by year. The mutual acquaintance of the two peoples with the cultural riches began in the XIX century.

It has been many years since the famous writer A. Qakhhor's Saldas became friends with German girls. “Sinchalak” has been published twice. The translator, E. Brumer, acknowledged A. Qahhor's skill and called him the “Master of Prose.”

Writer Arno Shpecht translated the novel “O‘tkan kunlar” by the famous writer Abdulla Kadiri and published it under the title “Die Liebenden von Taschkent” (Lovers of Tashkent) [1].

Translation is a powerful weapon that serves the interests of friendship, brotherhood and cooperation, between people, as well as economic-political, scientific, cultural and literary ties between them [5].

This is what the German literary critic N. Tun says about the novel and its author, which was warmly received by literary critics and readers. “Abdulla Kadiri, while preserving national traditions in his work, pays special attention to the artistic expression of new social problems, the development of a new literary language, the development of new visual aids, the clarity of thought and conciseness of words”. He said.

The German literary critic then covered the early years of the revolution and the development of Uzbek literature, Abdulla Kadiri's life and career, an analysis of the novel "O'tkan kunlar", and Abdulla Kadiri's contribution to literature. The author's acquaintance with the history of the Republic, the literary process, and his extensive reading of Uzbek literature were evident in his thoughts. N. Tun commented on Uzbek literature in the 1920s, and these years were the years of searching for new ways for Uzbek literature, the struggle for realistic prose. While A. Kadiri illuminates his creative path, the German researcher refers to many sources. A. Kadiri's work is in some places compared with S. Ayni's work.

Commenting on the importance of Abdulla Kadiri's novels, N. Tun concluded that the novels "Bygone Days" and "Scorpion from the Altar" had a great impact on the development of young Uzbek prose towards realism.

The critic concludes: "His (Kadiri's) novel, which he himself called 'a small experience, or rather a passion, has a strong place in the history of Uzbek literature.' [4] The views of another German literary critic, P. Kirchner, on the author of "Bygone Days" are noteworthy: The novel differs from these analytical works in that it depicts life realistically, with a variety of colors, melodies, and a variety of means of expression". The fact that N. Tun and P. Kirchner raised the issue of influence in the analysis of the Uzbek author's novel shows that Abdulla Kadiri's work is worthy of worldwide study [2].

Uzbek literature has never been more widespread and successful in its history. As the best examples of Uzbek literature are published abroad, foreign researchers, writers and critics write scientific pamphlets on the pages of prestigious journals and praise the translated works.

Finally, the novel "O'tkan kunlar" was translated into English by British literary critic Carol Ermakova [3]. The translation was edited by Julie Weekenden. Well-known Uzbek artist

Bobur Ismailov painted for the novel. The English version of the novel was published by the famous French publishing house Nouveau Monde Editions.

Well-known literary critic Shukhrat Rizayev noted that introducing the world to the "O'tkan kunlar" is to acquaint the peoples of the world with the Uzbeks, the heart, soul, mind, national world, customs, traditions and values of the Uzbek people.

It was an honor to translate this work into English. It should be noted that almost 100 years after its creation, "O'tkan kunlar" was translated into English by two Translators at the same time - British and American translators. This was an important step in the development of Uzbek literature and its introduction to the international community.

On December 27, 2019, at the Embassy of Uzbekistan in Washington, D.C., an American literary scholar, who translated "O'tkan kunlar" into English, one of the first volunteers of the Peace Corps in Uzbekistan, said in an interview with Mark Reese: For me, the criterion for assessing the level of a work is the ability of a great writer to convey his thoughts to all mankind, to each of us, regardless of the culture, language or historical period in which it was created. That is why it is called world literature. The works of Abdulla Kadiri and many other Central Asian writers are still not included in the list of masterpieces of world literature.

Abdulla Kadiri managed to cross the finish line. All I can say is that "O'tkan kunlar" is a very rich and complete novel, full of descriptions of different traditions, terms, and historical stories that are new to the Western reader. This is also an important step in introducing Uzbekistan to the world. An interpreter picks up someone's work and interprets it in a language that students of other nations can understand. Translation is not a science, but the art of conveying the author's thoughts. To make it easier for my readers to understand, I have included about 500 comments on important points in the novel.

I think Kadiri understood that very well. As well as writing masterpieces, he set out to expose the problems of his time. However, it should be noted that in this enlightened world, the destinies of all people are common, and that is why Kadiri addresses all mankind through his work.

To me, this novel reminds me of the works of William Faulkner and James Joyce. The prose of both writers is very rich and difficult to understand in one reading. These three authors lived at about the same time, creating a series of new ideas, and at the same time, looking back at their work and comparing it to the image of their time. They enjoyed the innovations of their time, were immersed in fame, and at the same time were not afraid of criticism.

- We want to get a grant for a program to translate beautiful works of Uzbek literature. After Qadyri's masterpiece, the first thing that came to my mind was the novel "Navoi" by Oybek. Under the name "Dialogue", I want to open an official cultural program to train young translators interested in Uzbek works, to discover new works. The goal is to introduce your rich literature to Western readers.

Work on the translation of the novel took more than fifteen years. Thanks to

the active support of the Embassy, our compatriots in the United States, as well as Uzbek experts, the process of publishing the novel has significantly accelerated. The book went on sale and received a five-star rating. The 660-page book contains more than 400 explanations of various terms and phrases used by the author, as well as explanations of the culture, customs and traditions of the Uzbek people.

According to the Uzbek embassy, copies of the book were distributed to US government officials, members of the diplomatic corps and leading US universities. The novel was also registered in the Library of Congress, the largest library in the United States and the oldest federal cultural institution.

At the end of the presentation, an agreement was reached with Mark Reese to discuss a project to translate Abdulla Kadiri's novel "Mehrobdan chayon" (The Scorpion from the Altar) after the presentation of the English translation of the book "O'tkan kunlar".

Thus, a great figure like Abdulla Kadiri, the legacy he left behind, entered the home of the people across the ocean and took a place in their hearts.

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